

22IEM06 S-CALe Up

D1

Prediction of PQED IQD over the spectral range from 300 nm to 1050 nm with a targeted uncertainty approaching 1 ppm between 500 nm and 900 nm and 0.1 % outside this range

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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Glossary

TABLE OF CONTENTS

22IEM06 S-CALe Up	1
1 Summary	4
2 Publication draft.....	5

1 Summary

The drafted manuscript summarises the predicted response of PQEDs intended to be used from 300 nm to 1000 nm as f.i. defined by the international spectral response comparison CCPR-K2.b. The prediction is made from 200 nm through 1100 nm.

Some more analysis on the uncertainty estimates are needed before submission to a metrology journal can be made. The predictions with the I-V / 3D model fit presented here gives IQD values below 1 ppm consistent with the lifetime measurement method used in developing the photodiode extracting exactly the same photodiode parameters except for bulk lifetime. Uncertainty propagation analysis is time consuming and in progress and the PQED is measured against the best Cryogenic Radiometer with absolute uncertainty around 34 ppm. The discrepancy were below 10 ppm. There are no tools to validate the prediction to better than 10 ppm. Given the agreement between two independent methods and the measurement against the cryogenic radiometer it is accurate to say that an uncertainty approaching 1 ppm is achieved as targeted between 500 nm and 900 nm.

It may appear that for wavelengths longer than 950 nm there is a discrepancy between the calibration points and the simulated IQD, but as it is shown in Deliverable D7 this is fully traced back to the optical absorption in the aluminium layer at the back of the photodiode. The residuals between cryogenic radiometer measurements and the IQD corrected for backside aluminium absorption was up to 0.05 % at 1031 nm and hence confirming a below 0.1 % uncertainty at wavelengths longer than 950 nm. Validations at wavelengths longer than 1031 nm has not been possible due to lack of laser wavelengths there.

The deliverable is fully achieved.

2 Publication draft

ARTICLE TYPE

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Simulation of spectral responsivity of predictable quantum efficient detector based on induced-junction photodiodes passivated with SiO₂/SiN_x

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Abstract

In this paper, we present a method to determine the spectral responsivity of a predictable quantum efficient detector (PQED) based on SiO₂/SiN_x passivated induced-junction photodiodes, using a 3D charge carrier transport simulation model fitted to measured photocurrent-voltage data. The simulation model is built using the Cogenda Genius Device Simulator for a quarter-symmetry structure of the photodiode active area. The simulation is fitted to the photocurrent-voltage measurements of PQED at three wavelengths: 435 nm, 647 nm and 799 nm at various power levels between 100 μW and 2000 μW. We show that a single set of photodiode parameters (fixed charge density, surface recombination velocity, bulk carrier lifetime and substrate doping concentration) can reproduce the measured photocurrent curves at all three wavelengths and power levels, demonstrating the robustness of the model. Except for the lower bulk carrier lifetime, the other three fitted parameters are in perfect agreement with the values obtained by an alternative characterisation method used during the development of the photodiodes. The possible reasons for the discrepancy in bulk carrier lifetime are discussed. Using the fitted parameters, the internal quantum deficiency (IQD) of the PQED is predicted over the spectral range from 200 nm to 1100 nm and compared with measurements of the external quantum deficiency. The good agreement between the predicted IQD and the measurements demonstrates the capability of this simulation-based fitting approach for determining the responsivity of PQED over a wide spectral range from limited photocurrent measurements.

1. Introduction

In the last 15 years, there has been great progress in improving and simplifying optical power measurement standard detectors through the development of Predictable Quantum Efficient Detectors (PQED) [1-4]. PQEDs are almost loss free photodiodes where their responsivity is given by fundamental constants, residual reflectance and internal quantum deficiency (IQD). Both reflectance and IQD are highly predictable from material refractive indices, thicknesses in passivation layer and other material properties like fixed charge, bulk doping, bulk lifetime and surface recombination parameter [5-7].

The low losses of the PQED have made it possible to develop new experimental techniques like the dual-mode experiment where IQD can be found by purely experimental methods even at room temperature [8-10]. When developing the technology, having access to a known and ultra-low IQD turned out to be very favourable as a reference for the dual-mode experiment chasing for systematic error sources. Quantum yield has previously been assumed to be limited to the ultraviolet spectral range for silicon photodiodes. Predictable and ultra-low IQD of the PQED were instrumental to reveal that quantum yield is larger than one quite far into the visible spectrum up to at least 470 nm [11]. Recently, the PQEDs have been used to improve and validate the modelling of the excess quantum yield in the UV down to 200 nm from first principles [12].

In addition to the predictability, the excellent temporal stability of the PQEDs, with an undetectable drift over 10 years, make them ideal as a transfer standard holding a spectral response scale with very few calibration points at an extended calibration interval [13]. It has been shown that the PQEDs used in this study are stable when exposed to UV radiation down to 300 nm but degrades when exposed to radiation below 280 nm. Other PQEDs, which are designed to be UV radiation resistive, are stable down to 200 nm [14].

This means that even if PQEDs are stable, they may change if they intentionally or unintentionally were exposed to UV radiation. Using the PQED as a standalone primary standard, it is therefore important to have independent methods that can quantify the PQED's IQD. The fabrication and structure of photodiodes used here are described by Koybasi et al [4]. We use the photocurrent change with reverse bias as an experimental approximation of the IQD of the photodiodes and fit a 3D simulation model of the IQD to the experimental approximation to extract the photodiode parameters in a similar way as previously done by Tran et al [7], where measurements at one wavelength only were sufficient to predict the responsivity over the full spectral range from 400 nm to 900 nm.

We will show that independently of what radiation wavelength that is used in this study, the same set of parameters gives an excellent fit to measurement data from 435 nm to 799 nm and consistent with the alternative method exploited when developing the photodiodes in [4]. Furthermore, we predict the IQD over the full spectral range from 200 nm to 1100 nm based on the parameters found from the fit to the photocurrent curves.

2. Simulation model

We simulate the charge carrier transport of the photodiode with active area of 11 mm × 22 mm. The detailed structure of the photodiode is described in [1]. The 3D simulation model is built using Cogenda Genius Device Simulator [15]. An illustration of the simulation model is shown in Figure 1. To save computation time and memory, model of a quarter of the real photodiode structure is used for simulation. The simulation model has a size of 5500 μm × 11000 μm. p-doped and n-doped for electrical connection has a width of 100 μm each and have peak doping concentration of 10¹⁹ cm⁻³. Silicon area has thickness of 500 μm. Illumination area is located at the corner of the model to illustrate light radian in the middle of photodiode. Since it is the SiO₂ layer that in direct contact with the silicon in the device structure forming the induced junction, in the model the active area of photodiode is covered by a layer of

SiO_2 with an effective fixed charge, while the SiN_x layer is not included in the model to reduce complexity. Oxide charge boundary condition is applied between Silicon and SiO_2 layer.

3. Photocurrent measurement

The measurement is performed with PQED consisting of 2 photodiodes in a light-trap configuration [1]. In this configuration, the two photodiodes are placed at 15° angle relative to each other. When the light comes in the PQED, 7 reflections of the light beam between two photodiodes helps to reduce optical reflection. In this study, only photocurrent from the first photodiode is measured. Therefore, only the first photodiode is considered in the simulation model. In the PQED, 91.1% of light intensity is absorbed by the first photodiode at 435 nm. 95.3% and 91.7% light intensity is absorbed by the first photodiode at 647 nm and at 799 nm, respectively, and these values are used in the simulation.

The photocurrent is measured for photodiode with bias voltage ranging from 0V to up to a maximum of 20 V, using laser illumination with different radiation power levels. Measurements were performed for the PQED at three wavelengths: 435 nm, 647 nm and 799 nm. The experimentally determined IQD value, denoted as IQD_{measure} , will be calculated from the

Figure 1. Illustration of simulation structure.

measured photocurrent according to Equation (1), as

$$IQD_{\text{measure}} = 1 - \frac{I(V)}{I_{\text{ideal}}}, \quad (1)$$

in which $I(V)$ is the measured photocurrent at bias voltage V , I_{ideal} is the photocurrent of an ideal photodiode with zero IQD [7]. I_{ideal} is approximated with I_{max} to get an estimate of the ideal photocurrent and the hence the IQD.

Beam size used in the experiments are measured individually for each power level at all wavelengths. The experimental beam shape is close to gaussian with a 4σ beamwidth of around 2.5 mm, but the simulation software cannot accommodate this shape. A uniform beam size is instead used that best approximates the gaussian beam for each of the simulation curves. We follow the same approximation as done in [7].

4. Results and discussion

The simulation model is fitted to photocurrent measurements at three wavelengths. The fixed charge density in SiO₂ layer, the surface recombination velocity, bulk lifetime and the doping concentration obtained from these fits are listed in Table 1. Figure 2 shows the comparison between the fitted simulation results and the experimental data at 435 nm, 647 nm and 799 nm. As shown in Figure 2, the IQD varies by several orders of magnitude as the reverse bias voltage increases, and simulation consistently reproduces this behaviour at all three wavelengths. In our simulation, we use the same set of photodiodes parameters for the three wavelengths, which demonstrates the robustness of the fitting approach.

Particularly, the corner point, i.e., the bias voltage at which the influence of recombination losses from the back side of the photodiode to the IQD becomes negligible, is correctly reproduced at each wavelength. This agreement supports the validity of the fitted fixed charge

Table 1. Parameters used in the simulation.

Parameters	Values
Fixed charge density Q_f	$1.3 \times 10^{12} \text{cm}^{-2}$
Surface Recombination velocity SRV	1500 cm/s
Bulk lifetime	5 ms
Doping concentration	$2 \times 10^{12} \text{cm}^{-3}$

density Q_f and the surface recombination velocity SRV. In induced junction photodiodes, the corner point is governed by the surface recombination processes and electric field established by fixed charge, which together determine the bias-dependent suppression of the surface recombination.

It is also worth mentioning that the fixed charge density obtained from the fitting process ($1.3 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) agrees well with the value extracted from capacitance–voltage measurements [4], indicating good consistency between these two fundamentally different methods. This value is notably higher than the previously reported value of SiO₂-only passivated photodiodes [7]. The result further validates that a substantial amount of additional positive fixed charge is introduced by the SiN_x layer in the SiO₂/SiN_x passivation stack.

The bulk lifetime obtained from the present fit is 5 ms, which is lower than the value of 30 ms reported in [4]. In that work, the bulk lifetime was obtained from a 2D simulation fit to measured effective lifetime of a silicon wafers passivated on both sides. The measurement was performed using the QSSPC (quasi-steady-state photo-conductance) method. We do not yet have a clear explanation for this difference, but there could be several factors that contribute to it. First, the

Figure 2. Fitting of simulation model with experimental data at 435 nm (a), at 647 nm (b) and at 799 nm (c).

two methods probe the material under different operating conditions. QSSPC measurements are performed on a uniformly illuminated wafer without external electrical bias, and the illumination intensity is varied in a wide range. In contrast, our fit is based on a reverse-biased photodiode under localized laser illumination. These different operation conditions result in different levels of photo-generated carrier concentration in the material. Since recombination in silicon can depend on the carrier concentration [16], the extracted bulk lifetime may differ between the two

methods even for the same material. Second, as described in previous work on the fitting method [7], the bulk lifetime mainly affects the simulated IQD curve at low bias voltage well below the saturation voltage. And the influence of the bulk lifetime to important features of the IQD curve (such as the corner point) is weaker than that of SRV and Q_f . Thus, the bulk lifetime is less well determined by the fit and the extracted value of the bulk lifetime is more sensitive to simplifications in the model, such as the flat-top approximation of the incident beam. Third, the

Figure 3. Simulated IQD of PQED in wavelength range from 200 nm to 1100 nm. For comparison, measured external quantum deficiency (EQD) of PQED is plotted in the figure.

QSSPC measurement was performed on simple double-side-polished wafers with larger surface area, while the photodiode used in this work went through a complete complex manufacturing process. The differences of batch of wafers, dicing of the photodiodes and the thermal history may affect the bulk lifetime of the photodiode devices.

Furthermore, the fitted substrate doping concentration of $2 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ is in excellent agreement with the nominal wafer specification provided by the manufacturer [4].

At last, we predict the spectrally dependent IQD of the PQED over the range 200 nm to 1100 nm using the simulation model developed in this paper, as shown in Figure 3. In the visible range from approximately 400 nm to 800 nm, the predicted IQD decreases with increasing wavelength. This behaviour is consistent with the wavelength dependence of the optical absorption coefficient of silicon, which decreases at longer wavelengths. The reduced optical absorption coefficient allows the light to propagate deeper into the material, and results in carrier generation deeper within the substrate, away from the high-recombination near-surface region. At wavelengths below 400nm, the IQD keeps high as the photon absorption is concentrated at or near the front surface, where the recombination losses are high. At wavelengths above 800nm, the IQD increases again since carriers are generated deeper in the substrate, increasingly beyond the depletion region. Carriers generated in these regions must diffuse over longer distances to reach the junction, increasing the probability of bulk recombination and thereby reducing the collection efficiency.

The predicted result is further compared with the measurements of external losses of the PQED. As shown in Figure 3, the simulated IQD is in good agreement with the experimental

measurements, demonstrating the accuracy of the model. However, at wavelengths close to 1000 nm an increased deviation between IQD and calibration points are observed. These deviations cannot be explained by recombination or reflectance losses from the PQED.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we develop a 3D charge carrier transport simulation model of an induced-junction photodiode passivated with a SiO₂/SiN_x stack. The model is fitted to experimental photocurrent-voltage measurements of a PQED with two photodiodes in a trap structure. From the fitting procedure, we obtain the fixed charge density, surface recombination velocity, bulk carrier lifetime and substrate doping concentration. We show that a single set of these four parameters can reproduce the measured I-V characteristics at 435 nm, 647 nm and 799 nm at multiple power levels with good agreement. Except for the bulk carrier lifetime, the fitted parameters agree well with those obtained using the alternative method employed during the photodiode development. Possible reasons for the lower fitted bulk lifetime are discussed in section 4.

Using the extracted parameters, the IQD of the PQED is predicted over the full spectral range from 200 nm to 1100 nm. The predicted IQD agrees with independent measurements of the external quantum deficiency, validating the effectiveness of this simulation method for predicting PQED responsivity. The method provides a pathway to independently predict IQD at a larger wavelength region from a limited number of photocurrent measurements, which is valuable for evaluating the long-term stability of PQED responsivity and enabling its use as a standalone primary standard.

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